

Relationships between measured and regression derived Carbon contents for different plant components based on tropical grassland species

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Abstract

Rising earth's temperature due to increasing amount of atmospheric CO₂ is a serious threat to earth's biodiversity and challenging. The long-term storage and exact quantification of Carbon (C) in available C pools are urgently needed to cut the risk of biodiversity loss arising from the global environmental change. Present study compared the measured C with regression derived estimated C for different plant components. For these 117 tropical grassland species just-before flowering were harvested from the campus of Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi. Oven dried biomass (B) and C contents for each species were determined using standard methods. Linear regression equations between C and B for different plant components were developed. Statistically significant regression equation between C and B for each plant component was used to estimate the C content. Data was analysed using suitable statistical approach. Results showed strong positive and linear relationship between C and B for each plant component. Stems had approximately three-times greater C than the roots. Across the components, the slope of the fitted regression equations varied between 0.42 and 0.47. The paired 't-test' showed insignificant differences between measured and estimated C for different plant components. Thus, the fitted regression equations could be useful for the quantification of missing C from tropical grassland which is a vital store house of biodiversity.

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Introduction

Globally, atmospheric Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is increasing at an alarming rate and its concentration in atmosphere has been suggested around 800-1000 ppm (IPCC, 2014). Being a major global warming gas, it has changed the spatiotemporal rainfall patterns, weather conditions and shifted the seasons (Singh, 2017). Currently, rising atmospheric CO₂ is one of the seriously challenging issues for the local as well as global biodiversity and environmental sustainability (Arora, 2019). Hence, global communities have felt to reduce the rate of CO₂ increase by storing in potential C sinks, viz; soil, above and below ground plant biomass, dead wood and litters (IPCC, 2014; Hill et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2015; UNFCCC, 2015; Odiwe et al., 2016). Current estimate suggested 1912.2 PG C for 1-m depth soil and 1415.7 PG C stored in above- and below ground plant biomass (Scharlemann et al., 2014), while a big uncertainty is persisting about the amount and accuracy of C stored in the terrestrial ecosystems

(Le et al., 2012) together with its residence time in plants (Friend et al., 2014) that's why about 0.4 - 4 Gt global C yr⁻¹ is estimated as a 'missing sink' (Gifford, 1994; UNFCCC, 2015).

The C stored in plants is determined by biomass inputs through photosynthesis along with its allocation in different plant components (Gifford, 1994; Ontl & Schulte, 2012) and outputs to senescence, mortality (Friend et al., 2014) and rates of decomposition of dead plant materials (Wang et al., 2013). Thus, determination of C content in different plant components is essential for accurate estimation of C stored in terrestrial C pools. The ecological research on C partitioning in different plant components is not only important for the assessment of competitive fitness, reproduction and growth of the plants against the climate change (Dickson, 1989) but also precisely contribute to the global total C estimation and prediction (Mokany et al., 2006; Russell et al., 2015).

The estimation of C stored in different grassland species is important because they cover nearly one fifth of the world's land surface area (Leith, 1978; Singh et al., 2006), harbour more than 90% plant species of the forest (Gilliam, 2007), represent more than 20 % of global total net primary productivity (Grace et al., 2006), contribute 50 % calories consumed worldwide (Irving, 2015) and store roughly 34% of the global terrestrial C pool (White et al., 2000). On the other hand, reduction in C storage capacity of tropical forests (Dunne, 2017; Ma et al., 2017) also necessitated to look herbaceous diversity as a potential C sink (Minahi et al., 1993; San Jose et al., 1998).

Field based harvesting methods, regression equations, C:B ratio and root (R): shoot (S) ratios are commonly used methods for C computation in different terrestrial ecosystems (UNFCCC, 2015; Sainju et al., 2017). Unfortunately, non-destructive method for estimating the C contents of herbaceous species is not much known. Moreover, the use of the IPCC default R: S for estimating the root C of grasslands locating in different ecological conditions may increase the discrepancy in the prediction of total C (Barbosa et al., 2012; Mokany et al., 2006). Thus, it is urgent to develop regression equations between C and B for different components of herbaceous species to estimate the C which could be helpful in formulation of strategies to mitigate the elevated CO₂ (Sims & Bradford, 2001; De Deyn et al., 2008) for the sustainability of tropical biodiversity because tropics support major plant and animal species and cattle population of the world (Donadeu et al., 2019).

The hypothesis of present study was to observe no difference between field measured and equation derived C contents for each plant component of the tropical grassland. The specific objectives of present study were to derive regression equations between C and B for different plant components and to compare the measured and equation based C contents based on 117 grassland species.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on the campus of [Banaras Hindu University](#) (24°18' N and 83°03' E and 80.71 m above sea level), Varanasi, India, during January 2014 - December 2015. The climate is a tropical monsoon. The cold winter (November to February), hot summer (April to June) and warm rainy (July to September) are different seasons. The months of October and March are transitional months between rainy and winter, and between winter and summer seasons, respectively ([Verma et al., 2015](#)). During the study period, the mean maximum temperature was 30.19 °C (range 8–44.6 °C) while the mean minimum temperature was 20.27 °C (range 6.4–30.8 °C). Agrawal & Mehrotra ([1952](#)) characterized the soil as Banaras Type III, which is alluvial, well-drained, pale brown, silty loam and inceptisol. In general, it is moderately fertile being low in available nitrogen and medium in available phosphorus and potassium with neutral to alkaline soil pH ([Sagar et al., 2008](#)).

A total of 117 mature herbaceous species (just before the onset of the flowering stage) was collected from the entire campus of the University. For each species 3-10 healthy individuals (depending upon the availability) were harvested. Each harvested plants were separated into root, leaf, and stem components ([Poorter & Bergkotte, 1992](#)). The plant fractions were oven-dried at 80 °C to constant weighed. The oven dried plant material was used to determine the ash content. Ash content was measured after combustion of the sample in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 6 h ([Singh et al., 2011](#)). C content was determined by using the loss on ignition method ([Mcbrayer & Cromack, 1980](#)) which is approximately 50 % of ash-free weight ([van Soest, 1963](#)).

One way analysis of variance was used to see the effect of plant components on the measured C contents. Linear regression equation between C (on Y-axis) and oven dried B (on X-axis) for each plant component was developed considering 117 species as data point to estimate the C content for a given B. The estimated C content based on regression equation was compared with that of experimentally measured C using paired 't-test' with the help of SYSTAT software ver. 13 ([SYSTAT, 2009](#)).

Results & Discussion

Across the components, measured C (g plant⁻¹) varied between 0.90 and 2.77 ([Table 1](#)). Analysis of variance exhibited significant differences in C contents due to components ($F_{2,1170} = 279, P < 0.0001$). Plant roots had low C whereas stems represented three times greater C than the roots ([Table 1](#)). For each plant component, results yielded significantly positive and linear relationship between C and B ([Figure 1](#)). Across the plant components, the slope of fitted linear regression between C and B varied between 0.42 (root) to 0.47 (stem). At plant component level, the percent

Figure 1. Linear and positive relationships between carbon and biomass for different plant components based on 117 grassland species in a tropical ecosystem.

discrepancy in C prediction ranged from 1.09 (stem) to 1.36 (leaf). Interestingly, the paired 't-test' suggested no difference between measured and predicted C contents for each plant component (Table 1). Less discrepancy in C prediction and insignificant difference between measured and predicted C using developed regression equation between C and B showed high usefulness of the established regression equation.

Table 1. Comparisons of measured mean Carbon contents (g plant⁻¹) with the predicted approach (using fitted linear regression equations shown in Figure 1) based on paired 't-test' for different plant components using 117 grassland species.

Plant components	Measured-C	Estimated-C	t-value	P-value
Leaf	2.21	2.24	-0.37	0.72
Stem	2.74	2.77	1.77	0.08
Shoot	4.95	4.96	0.29	0.77
Root	0.89	0.90	-0.31	0.76
Total	5.84	5.93	1.86	0.07

In a study, Davies et al. (2011) reported 42.02 % C of the dry biomass for the herbaceous species. Tumuluru (2015) assumed 42.08 and 43.92 % C of the dry weight, respectively for the switchgrasses and corn stover. Moreover, majority of local, regional, and global studies showed 35 to 65 % plant C based on the plant dry weight (Lewis et al., 2009; Fang et al., 2001; Blanc et al., 2009; Redondo-Brenes, 2007; Thomas & Martin, 2012) and as a mean it has been reported around 45% (Wang et al., 2013; Fang et al., 1996; Farrar et al., 2014). Thus, the observed C: B ratio in present study (0.42 to 0.47 or 42 to 47 % C of the dry weight) is comparable to other reported studies.

Similar to the present study, Poorter & Bergkotte (1992) also showed substantial variations in the C partitioning among different plant components. The analysis of average C partitioning into the different plant components showed three times greater C in stems than the roots which is also supported by the study of Irving (2015). Such pattern signified the dependency of the plant growth on the supply of C from the stems, and the nutrients and water from the roots. Moreover, the greater C in stem compared to root and leaf could be argued because of storage of greater biomass and lignin in the stem than the other components (Poorter & Bergkotte, 1992).

In prediction analysis for selecting a suitable model, it is crucial to test all realistic models as meticulously as possible against the known standards to avoid summary judgement based on a single data set (Colwell & Coddington, 1995) by the reason that the utility of a model generally depends on its strength to predict unknown value for a given known value (SYSTAT, 2009). Statistically; the higher correlation coefficient, lower standard error of estimate, least discrepancy in prediction (SYSTAT, 2009; Sagar et al., 2003) wide adaptability with minimum time and cost epitomize the performance and utility of the model (Colwell & Coddington, 1995; Xie et al., 2009). In prediction analysis, a maximum of 10 % discrepancy in prediction has been advocated for selecting a model in many computational and statistical analyses (NRC, 2012; Wang et al., 2013). Around one percent discrepancy in prediction observed in present study strengthened the confidence for the utility of the derived regression equation for predicting the C based on B reported in diverse tropical

grassland studies. Due to inherent simplicity, greater prediction accuracy (% accuracy = 100- % discrepancy) and consistent results; the C:B ratio could be used for the C estimation at large-scale tropical grassland.

The conservative field measurement methods may give precise data on B and C, but are destructive in nature, difficult, time-consuming, and costly to cover at large scale, hence, C:B ratio and the fitted regression equations could be helpful for the quantification of the missing C using B present in grey literature at the large-scale tropical grassland. It could be helpful for the policy makers to curb the increasing atmospheric-C for better human wellbeing and global biodiversity and environmental sustainability against the observed global climate change problem.

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